

A Simple Supply Chain Model Using Statistical Techniques with Solved Examples

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Abstract:

Efficient supply chain management is essential for reducing costs, avoiding shortages, and satisfying customer demand. This research paper presents a simple supply chain model using basic statistical techniques such as demand forecasting, mean, standard deviation, safety stock, and reorder point. The paper is written in simple language and includes solved numerical examples so that undergraduate students and beginners can easily understand the concepts. The study shows how statistics helps decision-making in inventory control and supply chain planning.

Keywords: *Supply Chain Management, Statistics, Demand Forecasting, Inventory Control, Reorder Point, Safety Stock*

Introduction:

A supply chain refers to the complete process of making a product and delivering it to the final user. It involves several stages, beginning with the procurement of raw materials, moving through production and storage, and finally reaching the product to sellers and customers. One of the major problems in supply chain management is uncertainty in demand and lead time. Statistics plays an important role in handling this uncertainty. By analysing past data, managers can estimate future demand, decide how much to order, and determine when to place an order. This paper focuses on a simple supply chain model using statistical tools that are commonly taught at undergraduate level.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objectives of this study are:

1. To explain a simple supply chain inventory model
2. To apply basic statistical techniques in supply chain decisions
3. To demonstrate the model using solved numerical examples
4. To present the concepts in simple and clear language

Supply Chain Model Description:

In this paper, a simple single-product supply chain model is studied. Customer demand is uncertain, but it follows a stable pattern and past demand data is available for analysis. The lead time for receiving goods is assumed to be constant, and shortages are not permitted. The main decisions in this model are deciding the quantity to order and determining the correct time to place an order. These decisions are made using basic statistical measures such as mean, variance, and standard deviation to manage demand uncertainty effectively.

Statistical Tools and Analytical Methods:

1. Mean Demand:

The average demand is calculated using:

Mean (μ) = (Sum of demand values) / (Number of periods)

2. Standard Deviation:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{[\sum (x - \mu)^2 / n]}$$

Higher standard deviation means higher uncertainty.

3. Safety Stock:

Safety stock protects against uncertainty in demand:

$$\text{Safety Stock} = Z \times \sigma \times \sqrt{L}$$

where:

- Z = service level factor

- σ = standard deviation of demand
- L = lead time

4. Reorder Point (ROP):

Reorder point tells us when to place a new order:

ROP = Average demand during lead time + Safety stock

Solved Numerical Examples:

Example 1: Estimation of Mean and Variability in Demand:

A retailer observes the weekly demand for a product as: 20, 22, 18, 25, and 15 units.

The average (mean) demand is calculated as:

$$\mu = \frac{20+22+18+25+15}{5} = \frac{100}{5} = 20 \text{ Units}$$

And the variance in demand is,

$$\sigma^2 = 11.6$$

Example 2: Calculation of Reorder Point:

Average daily demand = 20 units Lead time = 5 days
Standard deviation = 3 units Z value for 95% service level = 1.65

Safety stock = $1.65 \times 3 \times \sqrt{5} \approx 11$ units

Demand during lead time = $20 \times 5 = 100$ units

Reorder Point, ROP = $100 + 11 = 111$ units

So, a new order should be placed when inventory reaches 111 units.

Example 3: Application in Supply Chain Decision:

If the current inventory level is 120 units and daily demand is 20 units, the inventory will reach the reorder point in:

$$(120 - 111) / 20 = 9 / 20 \approx 0.45 \text{ days}$$

This means the order should be placed immediately to avoid stock-out.

Results and Discussion:

The solved examples show that statistical techniques help in making rational supply chain decisions. Mean demand provides an estimate of expected sales, while standard deviation measures risk. Reorder point and safety stock help balance customer service and inventory cost.

Using these simple statistical tools, even small businesses can improve their supply chain performance.

Conclusion:

This paper presented a simple supply chain model using basic statistical techniques. The model is easy to understand and practical to apply. Solved examples demonstrated how statistics helps in determining reorder point and safety stock. The study concludes that statistical analysis is a powerful tool for effective supply chain management.

References:

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